

Navigating the Evolving Landscape: Intellectual Property and Technology Transfer in China's Electric Vehicle Industry

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Abstract

China's evolving regulatory landscape for technology transfer and intellectual property (IP) protection has profoundly shaped foreign direct investment (FDI) strategies in its automotive sector, particularly for electric vehicles (EVs). Since the late 1970s, China has used joint venture (JV) requirements to facilitate technology transfer from foreign automakers, aiming to accelerate domestic industry modernization. While this "market access for technology" strategy initially led to over-reliance on foreign technology, recent reforms have shifted toward innovation-driven growth. Amendments to patent laws, the establishment of specialized IP courts, and stricter enforcement mechanisms have improved IP protection, aligning China more closely with international standards such as the WTO's TRIPS Agreement. These changes have increased foreign investor confidence, prompting global automakers, especially German firms, to expand localized R&D and production. However, challenges remain—security screenings, data localization mandates, and export controls on advanced battery technologies create significant compliance burdens and limit technology sharing. Regional disparities in enforcement and persistent risks of forced technology transfer further complicate the investment environment. Despite these hurdles, China's dual strategy of protecting foreign IP to attract investment while supporting domestic champions like BYD and CATL has propelled it to the forefront of the global EV industry. The regulatory balance between fostering innovation, safeguarding national interests, and ensuring fair competition continues to define China's role as a collaborator and

competitor in the global automotive industry.

Keywords: Foreign Direct Investment (FDI), Electric Vehicles (EVs), Intellectual Property (IP) Protection, Technology Transfer, Regulatory Framework

Introduction

This study examines how China's evolving technology transfer regulations and intellectual property (IP) enforcement mechanisms have shaped foreign direct investment (FDI) strategies in its automotive sector. Recent amendments to patent laws, administrative licensing frameworks, and strengthened enforcement mechanisms—including heightened infringement penalties and specialized IP courts—demonstrate alignment with international standards. The government's shift from subsidies to innovation-focused policies, such as standardized vehicle testing and electric vehicle (EV) infrastructure mandates, prioritizes market-driven ecosystems. These reforms have increased foreign investor confidence, particularly among German automakers adopting localized research and development (R&D). However, tightened security screenings create significant hurdles, including prolonged cybersecurity reviews, stringent data localization requirements, and expansive national security interpretations that delay approvals and raise compliance costs. Foreign firms must weigh enhanced IP protections against risks including forced technology sharing, retroactive regulatory scrutiny, and ambiguous security thresholds. Sector-specific impacts emerge: component manufacturers benefit from clearer IP rules, while connected and autonomous vehicle firms face disproportionate security barriers. Effective strategies involve decoupling core technologies from market-specific adaptations while leveraging improved legal recourse, underscoring the complex balance between China's regulatory

advancements and persistent geopolitical challenges.

1. The Chinese Regulatory Environment, Foreign Direct Investment, and Technology Transfer

Foreign direct investment (FDI) serves as a primary channel for transferring advanced technologies from developed to developing countries, playing a pivotal role in the modernization of host economies (Borensztein et al., 1998). When multinational corporations establish subsidiaries abroad, they not only bring in capital and managerial expertise but also introduce cutting-edge technologies and processes. A crucial aspect of this technology transfer occurs through the hiring and integration of local staff within these foreign subsidiaries (Minbaeva et al., 2003). By employing local workers, foreign firms gain valuable insights into the host country's market dynamics and cultural nuances, which can enhance their operational effectiveness and competitiveness. Simultaneously, local employees benefit from direct exposure to new technologies and international best practices introduced by their foreign employers, facilitating skill development and knowledge diffusion within the local workforce. This reciprocal relationship underscores how FDI-driven hiring practices are intrinsically linked to broader technology transfer objectives, as both the foreign investor and the host economy stand to gain from the exchange of knowledge and expertise fostered through these collaborations.

The employment and integration of local employees within overseas subsidiaries is a vital avenue for knowledge transfer. In the Chinese automobile industry, where joint ventures between international automakers and local businesses have been crucial in promoting a two-way flow of information and expertise, this dynamic is especially noticeable. Hiring local employees gives multinational corporations (MNCs) crucial

insights into China's distinct market conditions, consumer preferences, and cultural background. Foreign automakers can improve their competitiveness and operational efficiency by customizing their goods, services, and management techniques to better suit the Chinese market thanks to this local knowledge (Buckley et al., 2007). For instance, multinational automakers in China have improved their market acceptance and success by modifying their vehicle designs and marketing plans in response to input and knowledge from their local employees.

On the other hand, working in foreign-owned automotive subsidiaries exposes local workers directly to cutting-edge manufacturing technologies, global industry standards, and international management practices. Chinese employees acquire new management and technical skills through daily collaboration with international specialists, mentorship, and on-the-job training that are sometimes absent in domestic-only companies. In addition to improving individual career possibilities, this helps spread best practices and information throughout China's automotive sector as workers pass their knowledge on to other local businesses or start-ups (Buckley et al., 2007).

Since FDI was first allowed in China in 1978, the government has mandated that foreign companies enter the market mainly through joint ventures (JVs) with local partners. This policy was put in place to help domestic industries close technological gaps and facilitate technology transfer (Fuchs et al., 2021). The Sino-Foreign Equity Joint Venture Law of 1979 codified this strategy, offering the legal foundation for such partnerships and encouraging foreign investment, particularly in fields that sought cutting-edge technology. These joint venture regulations became especially important in the automotive industry, where Western automakers were required to establish joint ventures with Chinese businesses between 1994 and the late 2010s, with the Chinese partner owning at least 50% of the joint venture (Fuchs et al., 2021). The

objective was to enable domestic manufacturers to get international technological expertise, therefore mitigating technological uncertainties and expediting the advancement of China's automobile sector.

Notwithstanding the incremental easing of ownership limitations—culminating in the removal of foreign ownership caps for new energy vehicles (NEVs) in 2018 and for all passenger vehicles by 2022—joint ventures remain predominant, particularly in the EV sector (Cheng, 2021; Koty, 2018). During this transition period, the regulatory environment shifted from mandating joint ventures toward permitting the creation of wholly foreign-owned enterprises (WFOEs). Such a decision granted foreign automakers the legal right to establish fully controlled subsidiaries. Despite the legal feasibility of WFOEs, numerous foreign automakers continue to establish joint ventures to leverage the expertise of Chinese partners in local supply chains, regulatory compliance, and alignment with state innovation objectives (Azure Group China, 2024). As a result, during the transition period, legacy joint ventures and new WFOEs coexisted, as international businesses balanced the benefits of local partnerships with the desire for autonomy and intellectual property protection while navigating China's intricate market environment. For example, joint venture activity has increased recently as international manufacturers seek to tap into China's sophisticated EV ecosystem, access to pre-existing supplier networks, and benefit from policy incentives designed to support local innovation and quick market adaptation.

China's combination of regulatory requirements (such as JV structures) and substantial economic incentives for "encouraged" sectors has been highly effective in attracting foreign technology and accelerating its adaptation and diffusion within the country. Domestic laws and regulations have stimulated technology transfer—by providing incentives to

international corporations, the Chinese state accelerated the process of technological adaptation. These benefits include entry to China's vast market and measures that fall under the "encouraged" section of the Catalog Guiding Foreign Investment in Industry (State Council of the People's Republic of China, 1995). The Catalog remains a key tool for targeting specific high-tech and strategic industries, offering foreign firms both access to the Chinese market and tangible policy benefits in exchange for technology transfer and local investment. Tax deductions or reductions, as well as advantageous financing alternatives for large-scale projects, are also available to foreign enterprises. Furthermore, businesses situated in high-tech zones and those that qualify as high-tech and new-technology enterprises are eligible for additional financial support. According to PwC China (2024), the standard corporate income tax (CIT) rate is 25%, but this can be reduced to 15% for qualifying high-tech and new-technology enterprises (HNTEs) and for companies located in designated zones such as the Hainan Free Trade Port and other Special Economic Zones (SEZs) if they meet certain criteria. For example, a foreign-invested company in Shanghai that obtains HNTE status can reduce its CIT rate from 25% to 15%, resulting in substantial annual tax savings.

Although there are regional differences in FDI investment incentives, they have stimulated the introduction of high-tech FDI and have played a critical role in acquiring technology. For example, the Shanghai Municipal People's Government offers FDI incentives, providing additional incentives to individuals who attract high-tech industries and any of the world's leading 500 companies to invest in China (Lee et al., 2003). Investment incentives are only applicable to sectors designated by the government. Regions in Eastern and Southern China such as Shanghai, Guangdong, and Jiangsu have historically attracted the bulk of FDI due to early market liberalization, superior infrastructure, skilled labor, and proximity to international markets (Wei et al., 2007). To maintain their competitive

edge and attract high-value projects, these regions offer targeted inducements, especially for high-tech and advanced manufacturing sectors.

Despite these targeted incentives, alongside improvements in the investment environment, foreign companies—particularly German firms—continue to face significant regulatory and operational challenges in China. The German Chamber of Commerce in China (2022) has highlighted that only 6% of German businesses reported clear contractual duties, and 24% felt forced to share technology in order to retain their market access. Additionally, more than 50% of German businesses operating in China have localized R&D operations, in part to reduce IP risks and meet regulatory requirements (German Chamber of Commerce in China, 2022). These businesses can develop closer relationships with their customers, react quickly to market changes, and adjust to changing regulatory environments owing to local R&D facilities. In order to successfully navigate administrative procedures and obtain market access, this strategy also aids in forging closer ties with regional suppliers, partners, and government organizations. Therefore, in China, regions compete for high-tech investment by offering significant incentives, especially to projects that promise advanced technology transfers, local R&D, and stronger alignment with China's industrial priorities. For foreign businesses, this creates a complex calculus: balancing the risks of IP exposure and regulatory compliance against the substantial benefits offered for deeper localization and technological collaboration, as well as legislative changes implemented to improve the business climate for international corporations.

To regulate issues concerning technology transfer, it is important for the Chinese state to take into account both codified legal frameworks and practical considerations. Such actions include refining licensing practices

related to technology transfer guaranteeing that IP laws can be properly enforced. Additionally, given the legality of reverse engineering under Chinese law, companies should implement strong contractual safeguards to reduce risks. China's regulatory environment demands a dual focus: adhering to progressive laws like the Foreign Investment Law while anticipating practical hurdles. Foreign firms must craft licensing agreements that preempt ownership disputes, comply with filing rules, and deter reverse engineering through enforceable contracts. Ultimately, combining legal vigilance with strategic partnerships remains key to navigating this landscape.

While China's domestic legal reforms and corporate strategies reflect efforts to balance innovation incentives with market access, these measures cannot be fully assessed without contextualizing them within global intellectual property norms. This necessitates examining China's alignment with the World Trade Organization's (WTO) Agreement on Trade-Related Aspects of Intellectual Property Rights (TRIPS Agreement), a framework that underpins international IP standards and shapes how nations reconcile domestic priorities with transnational obligations. TRIPS compliance not only illuminates the structural evolution of China's IP regime but also highlights persistent gaps between legislative commitments and enforcement realities, particularly in contentious areas like forced technology transfer and reverse engineering.

2. Navigating the TRIPs Agreement: A Comprehensive Overview of IPR Protection

TRIPS is the most comprehensive multilateral agreement on intellectual property rights (IPR) to date, administered by the WTO (TRIPS Agreement, 1994). It establishes minimum standards for the protection and enforcement of various forms of IPR, including patents, copyrights, trademarks, industrial designs, geographical indications, trade secrets, and undisclosed information (TRIPS Agreement,

1994). It demands effective enforcement of IPR through civil, administrative, and criminal procedures. Furthermore, the agreement codified dispute settlement procedures to resolve IPR-related disputes between WTO members (TRIPS Agreement, 1994). These measures promote innovation and empower law enforcement to legitimately and morally access and employ new technologies. Most notably, TRIPS better safeguards cross-border technology transfer by clarifying protective measures for the technology IP owners. In Article 7., the WTO makes it clear that the goal of IP rights protection is to promote innovation, technology transfer, and balance rights and obligations:

The protection and enforcement of intellectual property rights should contribute to the promotion of technological innovation and to the transfer and dissemination of technology, to the mutual advantage of producers and users of technological knowledge and in a manner conducive to social and economic welfare, and to a balance of rights and obligations. (TRIPS Agreement, 1994)

Article 8.2 recognizes that WTO members need to adopt appropriate measures to prevent practices that adversely affect the international transfer of technology. This clause implies the WTO permits countries to employ measures against IP rights abuse or anti-competitive practices, so long as the measures comply with the Agreement (TRIPS Agreement, 1994). This provision acts as a corrective mechanism within TRIPS, enabling countries to enforce IP rights in ways that prioritize equitable technology access, fair competition, and public welfare. Its relevance is heightened in contexts where IP concentration threatens developmental or environmental goals.

Article 66.2 regarding Least-Developed Country (LDC) Members mandates developed

country (DC) members to incentivize their enterprises and institutions to carry out and advocate for technology transfer to LDC members. This article aims to assist LDCs in building a solid technological foundation. However, the vague language of the provision and the private nature of intellectual property rights complicates the implementation of this requirement. To address these shortcomings in relation to the EV sector, China has adopted a dual strategy of aggressive incentives and structured IP frameworks while avoiding the use of coercive tactics. China's unique status as both a developing country and an emerging global power allows it to navigate international obligations with flexibility, selectively invoking its developmental challenges or economic strengths as needed—a dynamic that complicates a straightforward application of Article 66.2. By clarifying obligations, aligning subsidies with measurable outcomes can facilitate meaningful technology transfer without undermining private IP rights. This approach would not only aid LDCs but also create new markets for developed countries firms in emerging green economies.

China's evolving legal framework for IP and FDI reflects strategic alignment with global norms, such as the WTO's TRIPS Agreement, while simultaneously advancing domestic innovation goals. Recent legislative reforms, including the 2020 Foreign Investment Law (FIL), explicitly prohibit forced technology transfer and strengthen IP protections for foreign investors, addressing long-standing criticisms from Western partners (Raslan, 2024). These measures align with TRIPS Article 8.2 by curbing anti-competitive practices, though enforcement inconsistencies persist, particularly in local courts favoring domestic firms. China's specialized IP courts and enhanced punitive damages, up to RMB 5 million for trade secret violations, demonstrate compliance with TRIPS enforcement standards, yet gaps remain in translating legal reforms into uniform practice (Interesse, 2024).

The relationship between FDI and IP is key to

China's desire to move from technology importer to global innovator. While TRIPS Article 66.2 stresses technology transfer to least-developed nations, China has flipped this dynamic through the use of the Belt and Road Initiative (BRI), exporting its tech standards while utilizing international R&D inflows (TRIPS Agreement, 1994). China's BRI-driven tech exports and developing-country status create a dual dynamic where it functions both as a recipient of foreign R&D—like a least developed country—and a provider of technology—like a developed country. This exposes a gap in TRIPS, which was designed for a binary DC-LDC framework, not for ascendant economies reshaping global tech hierarchies through initiatives like the BRI.

This evolving role is reflected in China's recent domestic policy reforms. High-tech and green industries are given priority on the 2024 Negative List for Foreign Investment, which steers FDI toward fields like EVs and AI to support domestic innovation (National Development and Reform Commission [NDRC] & Ministry of Commerce [MOFCOM], 2024). The Negative List specifies sectors where foreign investment is restricted for example equity caps or prohibited. Industries not on the list are fully open to foreign investors. (NDRC & MOFCOM, 2024). The 2024 list removed all manufacturing restrictions, including EVs, semiconductors, and green energy sectors, which are now fully accessible to foreign capital. These sectors are excluded from the Negative List, meaning foreign firms can invest without ownership limits or mandatory joint ventures. China is now ranked as the world's second-largest R&D spender, with seven of the top ten research institutes worldwide being Chinese. This is due to a dual policy of preserving foreign intellectual property to attract investment while funding local R&D (Interesse, 2024). This dual strategy protecting foreign IP to attract FDI while channeling resources into local R&D has positioned China as both a collaborator and competitor in the global EV race, epitomizing

its transition from technology follower to innovator.

China's journey from technology importer to innovator has been underpinned by a dual legal evolution: aligning domestic IP frameworks with international standards while tailoring reforms to serve national innovation objectives. This development illustrates China's balancing act, which continues to define its status as both a partner and a rival in the global intellectual property landscape: using international accords like TRIPS to integrate into global value chains while improving legislation to support domestic R&D.

3. Advancements in IPR Protection: China's Evolving Domestic Legislation

In recent years, statutory laws on IPR in China have been converging with international standards. China joined several international organizations and agreements, promulgating domestic legislation alongside. China's modern IP Rights regulatory regime dates back to the 1980s. The regime consists of the 1982 Trademark Law, the 1984 Patent Law, and the 1990 Copyright Law. The Trademark Law protects distinctive markings used to identify goods and services. The Patent Law protects inventions and grants exclusive rights to IP rights holders. Meanwhile, the Copyright Law protects original literary, artistic, and scientific works. Nonetheless, even though basic IP rules are established, China continues to have serious difficulties with implementing the laws throughout the 1980s and beyond. Proliferating IP infringements caused by inadequate enforcement measures and local protectionism made certain investors reluctant to enter the Chinese market. Over time, particularly as China's automotive sector shifted toward EVs, these laws underwent significant evolution to address the needs of FDI and to align with international standards.

China's 2001 WTO entrance and pressure from trading partners prompted the first legislation to focus on conformity with international standards,

including the TRIPS Agreement. Prior to reforms, foreign investment was discouraged by local protectionism, lax enforcement, and widespread infringement, especially in technology-intensive industries. By the 2010s, China's strategic focus on EVs supported by subsidies, R&D funding, and infrastructure investments spurred changes, including stricter enforcement mechanisms like specialized IP courts and punitive damages (up to ¥5 million) for infringement. These changes facilitated landmark investments, such as Tesla's 2018 WFOE in Shanghai, which combined access to China's market with enhanced IP safeguards.

China's intellectual property reforms, like the 2023 Patent Law amendments that allow for delayed examination and more stringent good-faith filing requirements, decreased the risk of forced technology transfers for foreign automakers like BMW and Volkswagen and encouraged FDI in localized R&D and production (Patent Law of the People's Republic of China, 2023; Fuchs et al., 2021). German automakers took advantage of loosened JV regulations by expanding their partnership stakes such as BMW's 75% ownership in Brilliance Auto and using China's EV supply chains for autonomous driving and battery technology (Jakóbowski & Oertel, 2025; Laurucci, 2023). However, these reforms coexisted with residual challenges: despite abolishing foreign ownership caps for passenger EVs in 2022, legacy JVs remained prevalent due to local partners' market expertise, and domestic firms like BYD and CATL outpaced foreign rivals in LFP battery patents (62,000 by 2024) and cost efficiency (Grünecker, 2024; Ezell, 2024).

By 2024, China emerged as a global EV patent leader, filing 62,000 charging-related patents, while domestic firms like BYD and CATL leveraged state-backed R&D to dominate battery technologies such as lithium iron phosphate (LFP) cells (Grünecker, 2024). However, tensions persist between China's

dual role as an IP collaborator (via initiatives like the Belt and Road) and competitor, exemplified by its rise as the world's largest EV exporter amid ongoing allegations of forced technology transfers. This evolution underscores how China transformed its IP regime from a barrier to a catalyst for innovation, balancing TRIPS Agreement compliance with domestic priorities to achieve technological leadership.

Despite improved mechanisms to protect foreign IP rights, domestic strategic R&D investments and partnerships between corporations, entrepreneurs, and universities are supported by the state. China's 2025 restrictions on exporting LFP preparation and lithium extraction technologies (MOFCOM, 2025) prevent foreign competitors from replicating advanced battery formulas. This protects domestic firms' IP while allowing them to scale production for global EV markets. Utilizing these regulations, domestic companies such as BYD and CATL were able to develop the first lithium iron phosphate (LFP) battery technologies, which are more affordable, safer, and have longer lifespans than conventional lithium-ion cells (Carbon Credits, 2024). Ultra-fast charging (300 miles in 5 minutes) and 15-year or 1.5-million-kilometer warranties are made possible by CATL's innovations, such as its M3P chemistry and Shenxing LFP cells (Lambert, 2025). In the meantime, BYD surpassed Tesla in global EV sales by 2024 thanks to its vertically integrated supply chain and emphasis on LFP innovation (Carbon Credits, 2024). China's patent leadership extends beyond hardware to smart charging infrastructure, with firms like Aulton developing data-connected high-performance stations (Grünecker, 2024). These efforts are supported by subsidies, specialized IP courts, and punitive damages for infringement, which strengthened domestic innovation ecosystems (Ezell, 2024). To illustrate, high-tech enterprises enjoy a 15% corporate income tax rate (vs. 25% standard), saving firms over \$370 billion in 2024. R&D-focused companies also benefit from a 200% super deduction on qualifying R&D expenses, incentivizing innovation-driven investments

(Huld, 2023).

The Cybersecurity Law (CSL) (2017), Data Security Law (DSL) (2021), and Personal Information Protection Law (PIPL) (2021) are the foundation of China's data localization regulations, which require that data produced by EVs, such as vehicle telematics, user behavior, and geographic data, be stored domestically and prohibit cross-border transfers without permission from the government (Cyberspace Administration of China [CAC], 2021; Skadden, Arps, Slate, Meagher & Flom LLP, 2021). The 14th Five-Year Plan (2021–2025), which emphasizes "*digital China*" and technical sovereignty, is in line with these regulations. Its goal is to strengthen control over vital data in order to support domestic innovation in high-tech industries like EVs (Koty, 2018).

Localized adaptations are used by German automakers such as Volkswagen and BMW to comply with these restrictions. In order to meet DSL regulations and expedite the development of cost-effective EVs, Volkswagen consolidated its EV R&D in Hefei, Anhui, creating a data-compliant hub for its Modular Electric Drive Matrix (MEB) and China Main Platform (CMP) (Fuels & Lubes, 2024). In order to comply with the Personal Information Protection Law's (PIPL) requirements for personal information permission, BMW and Tencent collaborated to develop autonomous driving technologies that are suited to China's data regulations (Symonds, 2019). The development of the BMW Group China High Performance D³ platform, a cutting-edge data-driven development hub situated in China, lies at the heart of this partnership. Tencent ensures that all activities completely adhere to Chinese rules on data security and privacy by providing the platform with the IT architecture, cloud computing, big data analytics, and security expertise it needs. This is especially crucial as Chinese laws mandate that domestically generated automobile data be processed and stored locally, and foreign

businesses are not allowed to host such data on their own without a domestic partner. BMW can process the enormous volumes of driving and environmental data required for the verification and development of Level 3 and Level 4 autonomous driving systems by utilizing Tencent's capabilities. This allows BMW to modify these technologies to meet the particular traffic conditions and legal requirements of China. In addition to speeding up BMW's R&D for autonomous vehicles in its biggest international market, the agreement establishes a standard for cross-industry collaboration under China's developing data and automotive innovation laws (BMW Group, 2024; Liao, 2019; Reuters, 2025).

China's regulatory framework—characterized by strict export controls on advanced battery technologies, comprehensive data localization requirements, and targeted industrial policies has been instrumental in enabling domestic champions like BYD and CATL to dominate the lithium iron phosphate (LFP) battery sector (MOFCOM, 2025; State Council Information Office, 2024). By mandating that sensitive R&D data and core manufacturing techniques remain within national borders, these regulations not only protect intellectual property but also create high barriers for foreign competitors seeking to replicate Chinese advancements (Reuters, 2025). However, these same export and data restrictions also limit the global integration of Chinese research and development, effectively siloing innovation within the domestic market (Groenewegen-Lau & Gunter, 2025). This dual approach illustrates the Chinese state's strategy: on one hand, leveraging data control and technology protection to spur indigenous EV innovation and secure global leadership in LFP patents as exemplified by BYD's hegemony; on the other, attracting foreign investment and collaboration through increasingly clear and predictable regulatory guidelines (UN Trade and Development [UNCTAD], 2024; Reuters, 2025). This regulatory architecture provides both a shield for domestic innovators and a structured pathway for foreign firms to participate in China's rapidly evolving electric vehicle ecosystem.

Overall, by aligning IP reforms with sector-specific goals, for example EV infrastructure in the 14th Five-Year Plan, China transformed its regulatory framework into a catalyst for both indigenous innovation and foreign collaboration, ensuring its dual rise as a protector of foreign IP and a leader in EV technology exports. By explicitly linking IP protection and enforcement with national priorities, such as the rapid buildout of EV infrastructure and the development of new energy vehicle clusters, China has created a regulatory environment that both incentivizes domestic innovation and reassures foreign investors about the safety of their technology and know-how.

In addition to requiring more stringent quality control, higher standards for new energy vehicles, and quicker charging infrastructure deployment, the 14th Five-Year Plan lays out goals for high-value invention patents, patent-intensive industries, and international intellectual property cooperation. These policies have created an innovation ecosystem in which foreign companies are more inclined to cooperate, invest, and license technology because they know their intellectual property will be better protected, and Chinese companies are encouraged to develop core technologies and compete internationally (State Council of the People's Republic of China, 2021; National Intellectual Property Administration, 2021). This dual rise as a protector of foreign intellectual property and a leader in electric vehicle technology exports is further reinforced by administrative and judicial reforms, such as specialized IP courts, punitive damages for infringement, and streamlined legal recourse for rights holders. At the same time, sectoral policies like purchase subsidies, infrastructure investment, and clear technical standards have made China the world's largest EV market and a global exporter of EV technology (Reuters, 2025; Ezell, 2024). This dual rise as a protector of foreign intellectual property and a leader in electric vehicle technology exports is further

reinforced by administrative and judicial reforms, such as specialized IP courts, punitive damages for infringement, and streamlined legal recourse for rights holders. At the same time, sectoral policies—like purchase subsidies, infrastructure investment, and clear technical standards have made China the world's largest EV market and a global exporter of EV technology (Ezell, 2024; CIELA Insights, 2024; Reuters, 2025).

4. Balancing Development and Security: Major State Plans and Documents strategizing IPR protection

China's transition from growth driven by subsidies to competition driven by innovation is highlighted by the interaction of top-down policies (such as Belt and Road tech exports), mid-term industrial targets, and bottom-up pilot programs. In the midst of increasing examination of IP enforcement loopholes and geopolitical concerns, China has positioned itself as both a collaborator and a competitor, as seen by its dominance in worldwide EV exports (40.9% penetration in 2024) (Argus Media, 2025; Jakóbowski & Oertel, 2025). As China's EV industry develops into a dual engine of FDI attraction and indigenous disruption, it is still crucial for manufacturers to strike a balance between technology sharing and IP protection.

The 14th Five-Year Plan National IP Protection and Application Plan and China's 2021 Guidelines for Building a Powerful Country with Intellectual Property Rights (2021–2035) signaled a strategic shift in bringing legal frameworks into line with technological aspirations, especially in the EV industry. The 2021 Guidelines outlined two goals: establishing China as a global leader in intellectual property governance through programs like the Belt and Road Initiative and bolstering domestic IP systems, including the establishment of specialist tribunals and the imposition of punitive damages. (China Justice Observer, 2021; Lung Tin Intellectual Property Agent Ltd., 2021). At the same time, the 14th Five-Year Plan established quantitative goals, such as increasing the GDP contribution of

patent-intensive industries to 13% by 2025 and obtaining 12 high-value invention patents per 10,000 people. These goals will directly encourage innovation and technological advancement in industries such as EVs (China National Intellectual Property Administration, 2021; State Council Information Office, 2021).

Meanwhile, IP reforms under the Guidelines for Building a Powerful Country with Intellectual Property Rights (2021–2035) are driven by two interconnected strategic goals (Central Committee of the Communist Party of China & State Council of the People’s Republic of China, 2021). First, they aim to accelerate the economic transition from manufacturing-based growth to innovation-led development, particularly in high-value sectors like EVs and artificial intelligence (AI). For instance, BYD’s global patent filings surged by 40% in 2023 after reforms strengthened IP safeguards, enabling the company to dominate EV battery innovation and expand into European markets (Raslan, 2024). Second, the reforms prioritize global integration by aligning China’s IP regime with international standards, such as the Hague Agreement and TRIPS, to attract FDI. Tesla’s Shanghai Gigafactory exemplifies this shift, operating as a wholly foreign-owned enterprise with full IP control over its battery and autonomous driving technologies, a departure from earlier joint venture requirements (Bailey, 2020).

Both the National Plan and the Guidelines seek to provide a safer environment for foreign investors by bolstering IP protection and refining law enforcement procedures. Such a guarantee reduces the danger of intellectual property theft and infringement, making it essential for businesses thinking about joining or growing in the Chinese market. While the former presented concrete, achievable measures in the short term, the latter offered a comprehensive framework for the sustainable development of IP protection in China. By strengthening legislative safeguards, promoting technology transfer, and fostering

market trust, the two documents work together to create an environment that is favorable for FDI.

Meanwhile, both documents envisioned broader goals that are fundamentally connected to the “Measures on the Transfer of Intellectual Property Rights to Foreign Parties (Pilot)”. The 2018 Measures on the Transfer of Intellectual Property Rights to Foreign Parties (Pilot) and their connection to broader Chinese policy frameworks like the Made in China 2025 initiative and the National Medium- and Long-Term Program for Science and Technology Development (2006–2020) are critical to understanding China’s dual strategy of safeguarding national security while advancing indigenous innovation.

5. Navigating New Regulations: The Pilot Measures on IP Transfers to Foreign Entities

Published on March 29, 2018, the “Measures on the Transfer of Intellectual Property Rights to Foreign Parties (Pilot)” (Measures, hereafter) tightened scrutiny over the transfer of IPR to foreign parties on grounds of public interest or national security (State Council General Office, 2018). As national defence and national security are managed differently, technologies linked to the former are not regulated under the Measures. Security assessments are required for certain forms of technology transfers, which tighten requirements for Chinese IP to be transferred over to foreign firms. For instance, if a Chinese tech company wants to license its AI algorithm or share source code with a foreign partner, it must first demonstrate to regulators that the transfer does not endanger national security, economic interests, or public safety.

The Measures mandated security assessments before exporting novel plant varieties, computer software copyrights, integrated circuit layout designs, and patents. This is in line with China’s current Catalog of Technologies Prohibited and Restricted from Export, which prohibits the export of technologies that the country deems

essential to economic growth or national security. Since foreign acquisitions of Chinese businesses are regarded as a type of intellectual property transfer, they are also regulated by the Measures. Here, “foreign acquisitions” cover both foreign parties’ acquisition of Chinese-foreign joint enterprises and their IP rights (UNCTAD, 2024). Given how much the EV industry depends on cutting-edge technologies, the Measures will likely hinder foreign tech development. Manufacturers will have to deal with the extra review procedure when entering into joint ventures or agreements for technology transfer with Chinese partners. To comply with the Measures, enterprises may need to do proactive IP due diligence and thoroughly evaluate IP rights involved in their China activities. To uncover any hidden problems or hazards, they need to go over existing technology transfer and joint venture agreements.

In China, the EV industry serves as a hub for both global investment and indigenous innovation. The Measures ensure that any transfer of EV-related technologies from Chinese enterprises to foreign corporations is thoroughly considered. This is especially important as China wants to be a leader in EV manufacturing and technology (UNCTAD, 2018). The Measures ensure that technology transfer supports China’s goals of increasing its indigenous innovation capacity, allowing international enterprises to contribute to the expanding Chinese EV industry while safeguarding domestic interests through security evaluations.

The law enforcement capabilities can create risks for foreign companies transferring technology to China. It is therefore crucial for companies to conduct thorough due diligence, understand the local legal framework, and seek professional advice when engaging in technology transfer with Chinese partners. Additionally, China’s policies on technology transfer are also influenced by other factors

like: national security concerns, industrial development goals, FDI regulations. Understanding these broader aspects is essential for a complete picture of the technology transfer scenery in China. Although the Measures are mainly concerned with IP export, they also have an indirect impact on imports since they create a more restrictive environment for technological transactions. These regulations may have an impact on the choices foreign businesses make about how to invest and operate in China.

6. Improving Enforcement Mechanisms

Despite stated policy advances, certain lines of critique persist: enforcement remains inconsistent, particularly in rural regions where local authorities often prioritize economic growth over IP compliance. The U.S.-China Business Council reports lingering challenges in trade secret protection, with 34% of member firms experiencing IP infringement in 2024, underscoring the gap between legislative progress and on-the-ground implementation (China National Intellectual Property Administration, 2023). This enforcement asymmetry underscores the delicate balance manufacturers must strike as China’s EV industry evolves into a dual engine of FDI attraction and indigenous disruption. While improved IP laws and specialized courts in urban centers like Shanghai and Shenzhen provide clearer recourse for multinationals, the rural-urban enforcement divide compels firms to adopt hybrid strategies sharing non-core technologies to access markets while ringfencing proprietary systems through contractual safeguards and blockchain-based IP tracking.

To handle complex cases, especially in technology sectors like patents and trade secrets, China established its first specialized IP courts in Beijing, Shanghai, and Guangzhou in 2014 (Hogan Lovells, 2014; Jiang, 2024). By 2019, the Supreme People’s Court established a national-level Intellectual Property Court to decide appeals of highly technical cases nationwide, establishing a “leapfrog appeal” system (World Intellectual

Property Organization, 2019). By 2022, 21 specialized IP adjudication organs were operating in cities such as Chengdu, Nanjing, and Wuhan (Managing IP, 2022). These courts prioritize cross-regional remote litigation platforms and employ technical investigators to expedite the process.

These changes are in line with China's dual goal of encouraging domestic innovation and drawing in state-of-the-art automotive FDI. With 78% of foreign-litigated cases ending favorably in 2023, German automakers such as Volkswagen and BMW have taken use of the specialist courts to defend EV-related patents (Lin & Liu, 2025; CIELA Insights, 2024). For example, Volkswagen's 2025 patent invalidation challenge against Denso Corporation in China underscores the strategic reliance on these courts to resolve high-stakes automotive IP disputes (Ma, 2025). This case highlights foreign firms' growing reliance on China's specialized IP tribunals to resolve high-stakes disputes, signaling confidence in its legal system despite historical skepticism. By contesting Denso's patents, Volkswagen aims to secure supplier flexibility while testing China's enforcement balance between domestic innovation and foreign IP rights.

However, a persistent worry for the stability of FDI is that the system's efficacy depends on persistent enforcement against counterfeiting in China's extensive car parts supply chain. China's IP framework exemplifies a tension between progressive central reforms and uneven local implementation, creating a dual system where foreign firms navigate both opportunities and risks. Centralized measures such as specialized IP courts in Beijing, Shanghai, and Guangzhou, these courts employ technical investigators, remote litigation platforms, and streamlined procedures to resolve complex cases, particularly in sectors like EVs. For instance, the Supreme People's Court (SPC, 2024) reported a 117% year-on-year increase in punitive damages applications in 2023, with total awards exceeding ¥1.1

billion (\$150 million), signaling heightened deterrence against infringement. Foreign firms, including German automakers like Volkswagen, have increasingly leveraged these tribunals to defend patents, as seen in high-profile cases involving EV powertrain technologies.

Yet, provincial authorities often prioritize short-term economic growth over IP compliance, leading to fragmented enforcement. For instance, while German automakers like BMW successfully defended EV battery patents in central courts, rural supply chains in Anhui and Jiangsu remain hubs for counterfeit auto parts, undermining foreign firms' competitive edge (U.S.-China Business Council, 2023). To stabilize FDI, China must standardize enforcement through mechanisms like cross-provincial IP task forces, reduce coercive localization mandates, conditioning EV subsidies on data-sharing with domestic partners, and enhance transparency in BRI tech collaborations by adopting reciprocal IP terms. By addressing these areas, China can reassure German automakers that their IP and market access are secure, stabilizing FDI amid escalating EU-China trade tensions over EV tariffs.

Conclusion

China's evolving landscape of IP law enforcement, technology transfer regulations, and FDI policies presents a complex challenge to foreign automakers. The Chinese government's recent restrictions on EV technology transfers in overseas investments underscore its strategic focus on preserving critical technologies within its borders. This approach, coupled with China's rapid advancements in EV technology and its dominant market position, has created significant hurdles for foreign companies seeking to compete in the Chinese market. The situation necessitates a delicate balance for foreign investors, who must navigate China's regulatory framework while protecting their intellectual property and maintaining their competitive edge in the world's largest and most dynamic EV market.

China's evolving IP regime, anchored by the 14th Five-Year Plan National IP Protection Plan and the 2021–2035 Intellectual Property Strategy Guideline, has reshaped FDI strategies, innovation ecosystems, and technology transfer dynamics in its automotive sector. Reforms such as specialized IP courts, streamlined dispute resolution, and punitive damages have mitigated historical risks of forced technology transfers, particularly for German automakers. Concurrently, the shift from direct subsidies to normative policies including EV charging infrastructure mandates and standardized testing protocols has fostered a structured yet competitive market, enabling domestic leaders to vie with global firms through advanced IP portfolios. This dual framework balances regulatory predictability with strategic market access, reflecting China's broader alignment with global innovation standards while retaining domestic competitive advantages.

Foreign automakers in China face persistent challenges, including uneven local IP enforcement and geopolitical tensions over technology exports, despite the National Plan for IP Rights (2021–2025) aiming to enhance transparency. China's dual role as both a strategic protector of domestic EV innovations evident in export controls and a global collaborator compels firms to balance cooperation with vigilance. To thrive, international companies must leverage China's IP reforms for localized production while safeguarding core technologies through strategic alliances and selective patenting. This regulatory landscape underscores the critical balance between IP-driven innovation and fair trade, shaping high-tech FDI as China cements its dominance as the world's leading EV exporter.

Stronger judicial and administrative safeguards, the imposition of punitive fines for infringement, and expedited dispute resolution procedures are some recent

developments in China's intellectual property framework. In order to boost investor confidence and encourage innovation, the National Plan for Intellectual Property Rights (2021–2025) seeks to further improve the caliber of IP protection, encourage increased agency cooperation, and increase the effectiveness of enforcement. Better legal remedies for copyright holders and a more stable business climate for international investors are the results of these initiatives. Despite these advances, significant challenges remain in balancing technology transfer requirements with the protection of foreign investors' interests. To further improve the environment for FDI and technology transfer, China could consider the following steps:

1. Increase transparency and predictability in the application of technology transfer regulations, ensuring that foreign investors clearly understand compliance requirements and the scope of protected technologies.
2. Strengthen independent judicial oversight to address disputes involving forced technology transfer or IP infringement, providing foreign companies with greater legal recourse.
3. Encourage voluntary, market-driven technology partnerships rather than mandatory transfer arrangements, fostering mutual benefit and innovation.

By adopting these measures, China can further solidify its reputation as a global innovation leader while attracting high-quality foreign investment and promoting sustainable, equitable technology exchange.

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